

ANTIMICROBIAL ACTIVITY OF CHITOSAN NANOPARTICLES AGAINST *STAPHYLOCOCCUS AUREUS* ISOLATED FROM MASTITIC MILK

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Abstract

Bovine mastitis caused by *Staphylococcus aureus* (*S. aureus*) is a major concern in the dairy industry, leading to economic losses and potential public health risks. The emergence of antibiotic-resistant *S. aureus* strains necessitates the development of alternative therapeutic strategies. This study investigates the antimicrobial activity of chitosan nanoparticles (CNPs) against *S. aureus* isolated from mastitic milk samples.

CNPs were prepared using the ionic gelation method and characterized for size and surface charge by dynamic light scattering (DLS), and zeta potential analysis. Their antibacterial activity was evaluated using the agar well diffusion, minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) and minimum bactericidal concentration (MBC) assays. The effect was also explored through morphological observations in scanning electron microscopy (SEM).

CNPs exhibited significant antibacterial activity against *S. aureus* in agar well diffusion, with MIC and MBC values 40 µg/mL and 80 µg/mL, respectively. In CNP-treated cells, SEM images revealed surface disruptions and deformations. These findings suggest that CNPs disrupt the *S. aureus* membrane, leading to cell death.

This study highlights the potential of CNPs as a promising approach for combating *S. aureus* infections in dairy animals. Further research focusing on in vivo efficacy, formulation optimization, and safety evaluation is warranted for their potential application in bovine mastitis treatment.

Key words: Mastitis, chitosan, nanoparticle, *S. aureus*, antimicrobial activity.

1. Introduction

Bovine mastitis, the inflammation of mammary glands in dairy cows, is a major economic burden for the dairy industry (Pal et al., 2020; Asfaw and Negash, 2017). It leads to decreased milk production, increased veterinary treatment costs, and potential milk quality issues. *Staphylococcus aureus* (*S. aureus*) is a significant mastitis pathogen, causing both acute and chronic infections (Gogoi-Tiwari et al., 2017; Campos et al., 2022). The widespread and often inappropriate use of antibiotics in dairy farms has accelerated the emergence of antibiotic-resistant *S. aureus* strains, posing a serious threat to animal and potentially human health (Almansour et al., 2023). This creates a critical need for novel therapeutic strategies to combat *S. aureus* infections in dairy animals.

Chitosan, a natural biopolymer derived from chitin having *N*-acetyl glucosamine and glucosamine units, has emerged as a promising candidate due to its inherent antimicrobial properties (Azmana et al., 2021; Peter et al., 2021; Kumar et al., 2020). Chitosan possesses a positive charge that interacts with the negatively charged bacterial cell membrane, leading to cell wall disruption and leakage of cellular contents (Liu et al., 2004; Yan et al., 2021). Additionally, chitosan nanoparticles (CNPs) offer several advantages over bulk chitosan. Their small size allows for enhanced penetration and interaction with bacterial cells, potentially leading to increased efficacy.

This study investigates the antimicrobial activity of chitosan nanoparticles against *S. aureus* isolated from mastitic milk samples. We evaluate the minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) and minimum bactericidal concentration (MBC) of CNP formulations against *S. aureus* strains. Furthermore, we explore the mechanism of action of CNPs on *S. aureus* by examining their impact on membrane permeability and morphology.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Chemicals and media

All the chemicals (analytical grade), microbiological media, and antibiotics were obtained from Merck Ltd., SRL Pvt., Ltd., Mumbai, and HiMedia Laboratories, India. Milli Q (MQ) water was used in the entire study.

2.2. Bacterial Strains and Milk Samples

A strain of penicillin-resistant *S. aureus*, previously isolated in our lab from a chronic mastitis case was thoroughly characterized culturally, biochemically, and genotypically (*spa* typing: t7867). *S. aureus* isolate was stored at -20°C in glycerol stocks for further analysis.

2.3. Synthesis and Characterization of Chitosan Nanoparticles

Chitosan nanoparticles were prepared using the ionic gelation method as per Iswanti et al., 2019. Briefly, 63 mL chitosan solution was prepared at 1 mg/mL concentration in 1% acetic acid. Then 27 mL aqueous solution of sodium tripolyphosphate (TPP) of 1 mg/mL was added dropwise under

constant stirring. The resulting CNP suspension was dialyzed against deionized water to remove excess acetic acid. The size and zeta potential of the CNPs were determined using dynamic light scattering (DLS) and zeta potential analyzer (Malvern, UK), respectively.

2.4. Antibacterial activity of CNPs

2.4.1. Agar well diffusion assay

The antibacterial activity of CNPs was assessed by the agar well diffusion assay method described earlier (Arshad et al., 2022) with slight modification. Briefly, in the Mueller Hinton agar (MHA) plates, seven 6 mm diameter wells were made equidistantly. Further, the overnight grown culture of the *S. aureus* was diluted to 0.5 McFarland Standards $\sim 1-2 \times 10^8$ colony-forming units (CFU) per milliliter, spread uniformly over the agar plate. The CNPs solution (320 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$) was diluted 2-fold and inoculated 50 μL gradually in the 5 wells, keeping the 6th well as a positive control (50 μL Cefoperazone, 75 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$) and 7th well as a negative control (50 μL MQ water), followed by incubation at 37°C temperature for 24 hr. Measuring the zone of inhibition (ZOI) by a standard transparent scale HiAntibiotic ZoneScale™-C (HiMedia Laboratories Pvt. Ltd. India), antimicrobial activity was interpreted.

2.4.2. Evaluation of MIC and MBC

MIC of CNPs was assessed using the micro-broth dilution method (CLSI, 2012) in 96-well tissue-culture grade microtiter plates (MTP), with slight modifications. Serial two-fold dilutions of the CNPs solution (25 μL in each well) with concentrations ranging from (0.0781 to 160 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$) were prepared in the wells of the 96-well microtiter plates using Mueller Hinton broth (MHB). Each well added 25 μL of the 0.5 McFarland standards bacterial suspension and 50 μL MHB. Positive controls (bacterial suspension without the CNPs) and negative controls (MHB without bacteria) were included in the microtiter plate. The microtiter plate was covered and incubated at 37°C temperature for 24 hr. The MIC was determined as the lowest concentration of CNPs that inhibited visible bacterial growth while the MBC was determined as the lowest concentration of CNPs that resulted in a $\geq 99.9\%$ reduction of the initial bacterial population. To assess MBC, from the wells used for MIC determination, samples were taken with concentrations equal to or higher than the MIC. These samples were spread onto sterile agar plates using a sterile spreader, followed by incubation at 37°C temperature for 24 hr, and then the number of CFU on each plate was counted.

2.4.3. Tolerance assay

The tolerance level was determined as per the following formula:

$$\text{Tolerance} = \text{MBC}/\text{MIC} \quad (\text{May et al., 2006})$$

2.4.4. Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM)

The morphological changes in *S. aureus* cells treated with CNPs were observed using scanning electron microscopy (SEM). Bacterial cultures were treated with CNPs for 12 hr were, fixed, and coated with a thin layer of gold. SEM images were then captured to visualize the surface morphology of the treated bacteria by an EVO18 scanning electron microscope (Zeiss, Germany) at an operating voltage of 15 kV.

2.5. Statistical Analysis

All experiments were performed in triplicate, and data were expressed as mean $\pm$ standard deviation of the mean (SD). Statistical analysis was performed using the SPSS software (SPSS v20.0, USA). P values < 0.05 were considered statistically significant.

3. Results

3.1. Characterization of Chitosan Nanoparticles

DLS analysis confirmed the successful preparation of CNPs with a Z-Average (d-nm) of 48.61 nm. Zeta potential measurements revealed a positive surface charge on the CNPs ($+34.05 \pm 8.7$ mV), a crucial factor for their interaction with negatively charged bacterial membranes.

Fig. 1. Hydro-dynamic size distribution (by number) of CNPs by dynamic light scattering (DLS).

3.2. Agar well diffusion (AWD) assay

The antibacterial activity of AgNPs against *S. aureus* growth was assessed by measuring the ZOI. In the present study, on MHA plates 18.17 ± 0.76 mm, 16.67 ± 0.61 mm, 14.1 ± 0.66 mm, 12.50 ± 0.10 mm, 09.47 ± 1.01 mm, and 32.2 ± 0.23 mm diameter ZOI was observed by CNPs concentration ranging from (320, 160, 80, 40, 20 $\mu\text{g/mL}$), and 75 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ cefoperazone, respectively. No ZOI was observed in control wells of MQ water. The gradual increase in the concentration of CNPs significantly ($P < 0.05$) increases the ZOI (Fig.2, Table 1).

Fig. 2. Zone of inhibition (ZOI) by gradient concentration of CNPs against *S. aureus*. The graph depicted the gradual increase in ZOI as the CNPs concentration increases by keeping Cefoperazone (75 µg/mL) as standard.

3.3. MIC and MBC of Chitosan Nanoparticles

CNPs exhibited significant antibacterial activity against *S. aureus*. The MIC and MBC values were 40 µg/mL and 80 µg/mL, respectively. However, the observed MIC and MBC values were slightly higher than cefoperazone against *S. aureus* isolate, suggesting the potential effectiveness of CNPs. Tolerance level was found to be 2.

Table 1. MIC, MBC, AWD values of CNPs against *S. aureus* strain

Parameters	Value
MIC (µg/mL)	40
MBC (µg/mL)	80
Tolerance (MBC/MIC)	2
AWD (mm)	20 µg/mL - 09.47 ± 1.01 40 µg/mL - 12.50 ± 0.10 80 µg/mL - 14.1 ± 0.66 160 µg/mL - 16.67 ± 0.61 320 µg/mL - 18.17 ± 0.76

3.4. Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM)

SEM images revealed significant morphological changes in *S. aureus* cells treated with CNPs compared to control cells (Fig. 3). The control cells displayed a smooth and intact cell surface. In contrast, CNP-treated cells exhibited surface irregularities, including craters, depressions, and even complete membrane rupture. These observations further support the notion that CNPs disrupt the bacterial membrane, leading to cell death.

Fig. 3. Effect on *S. aureus* cells observed by SEM. (a) *S. aureus* control; (b) *S. aureus* treated with CNPs.

4. Discussion

This study demonstrates the promising potential of chitosan nanoparticles as a novel therapeutic strategy against *S. aureus* infections in dairy animals. The prepared CNPs exhibited significant antibacterial activity against *S. aureus* isolates from mastitic milk samples. In agar well diffusion assay gradual increase in the CNPs concentration led to significantly increased ZOI. The MIC and MBC values were slightly higher than the cefaperazone, suggesting the potential effectiveness of CNPs, particularly against emerging antibiotic-resistant strains. Tolerance level value equal to or less than 4 depicted the microbicidal nature of CNPs. The CNPs disrupt the *S. aureus* membrane integrity. SEM images further confirmed the morphological alterations in the bacterial cell surface, including membrane disruptions and deformations. Similar findings were found by Yan et al. (2021) & Liu et al. (2004). These observations confirm that the positive charge on the CNPs interacts with the negatively charged bacterial membrane, leading to electrostatic attraction and disruption also depicted by Zhu et al (2018). This study provides valuable insights into the potential application of CNPs for bovine mastitis treatment. However, further research is needed to explore their efficacy in vivo models of mastitis. Additionally, the safety and biocompatibility of CNPs for use in dairy animals require thorough investigation.

In vivo studies in animal models of mastitis are crucial to evaluate the therapeutic efficacy of CNPs against *S. aureus* infections under practical conditions. Formulating CNPs for intramammary delivery through optimization of their size, surface charge, and controlled release properties is essential for their practical application. Investigating the potential synergistic effects of CNPs with conventional antibiotics could be explored to enhance their antibacterial activity and potentially reduce antibiotic use. A comprehensive safety assessment of CNPs in dairy animals, including potential side effects and milk residue analysis, is necessary before their implementation.

Conclusion

This study enlighten the potential of chitosan nanoparticles as an supportive or complementary strategy for combating *S. aureus* infections in dairy animals keeping in mind the rise in anti-microbial resistance. CNPs exhibited significant antibacterial activity against *S. aureus* isolates from mastitic milk, with evidence suggesting membrane disruption as the primary mechanism of action. Further research focusing on in vivo efficacy, formulation optimization, and safety

evaluation is needed to pave the way for the potential application of CNPs in bovine mastitis treatment.

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Conflict of Interests

The authors declare that there is no conflict of interest regarding the publication of this paper.

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